

**NATIONAL SECURITY & SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT:
PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES.
HUMAN SECURITY AS ANTIDOTE TO INSECURITY.**

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Abstract

The prevalent notion of insecurity as inadequate 'policing' and protection misses the point. Without tackling the underlying drivers of abject poverty and lack of opportunities, efforts aimed at 'investing' billions of naira at national security challenges can only produce same result as in the past money down the drains. If the national responses to security challenges are to be effective and sustainable, approach to insecurity has to be reviewed to contain one that addresses the forgotten issues...Human Security. This unrecognised aspect of national security is what this paper seeks to shed light on.

INTRODUCTION

The dominant view on national security is the primacy of the security of a federation and its sovereignty and territorial integrity in addition to the lives, liberties and property. According to Abubakar, "Some of the major security problems currently confronting the nation include: political and electioneering conflicts, socio-economic agitations, ethno-religious crises, ethnic militias, boundary disputes, cultism, criminality and organised crimes" (2007).

The prevailing notion above illustrates security as need for adequate policing for defence and protection of the nation from threats. This notion is not all inclusive as national security is also a state or condition where our values, beliefs, governance, unity, way of life, welfare and well-being as a nation and people are protected and

continuously enhanced. It should also be noted that focus on protection alone is not the way forward for national security. Rather, continuous enhancement also extends to prevention, response and rebuilding.

Equating security to policing highlights security to be focused on the armament of the governmental protection agencies, i.e. military, police and secret service and emphasises defence. This view is narrow and seems to contain all other existing insecurity issues in the blind spot. There is need for the redefinition of national security to one more people-centred, one which recognises the need to protect a nation's people from threats other than just physical insecurity, and one which not only protects but also empowers people and societies. All of these in a manner which will result in tackling the causative aspect of insecurity as opposed to focusing on defence which is more of a reactive attitude. This is human security.

This unrecognised aspect of national security is what this paper seeks to shed light on. The justification is that human security is the aspect which focuses on poverty, lack of opportunities, poor education, unemployment, and many more are actually representations of the root causes of insecurity.

The stance this paper takes is that human security, i.e. a people-centred view and approach is necessary to achieve national security. If the causes of insecurities are not tackled, then the government continuing to put huge sums into what it perceives as national security will only produce the same results witnessed in the past, money down the drains.

The immense importance of national security is evident in Esiemokhai's statement that "in an environment where development is security, and security is development, the consequences of such (insecurity) acts catch up very quickly with the system" (2010). The contribution this presentation seeks to make is to bring forth new insights within the context of national security beyond: physical insecurity, events seeking military or police intervention and into human security, a more encompassing and effective method to address national security given its 'from the beginning to the end' approach. The ultimate objective of this paper is to describe

how human security can be more effective and sustainable solution to insecurity. The format of this paper hereon, is to describe the current perception of what national security is, then highlight the realistic view of what national security truly entails, and then a look on how human security is the way forward.

The National Security Question - Perception

When most discuss national insecurity, their perception of addressing it is usually through policing and military armament. A typical example is Esiemokhai (2007) who suggested overt and covert military and under-cover operations measures should be taken. This has led to huge financial implications given the amount being invested in security institutions.

The proof of this is evident in Nigeria's budgetary proposal allocations. In 2012, out of a total of 4.74trillion Naira proposal, a whopping 921.91billion Naira was allocated to security. This is for the ministries, departments and agencies under the institution (Abubakar & Hassan 2011; Iredia 2011). Meanwhile in 2010, with a total budget of 4.07trillion naira, total allocation for security was 448.39billion Naira (with 231.99 towards defence and 216.4 billion naira towards police formation) (Sammyshow 2010). That is, within 2 years national security requirements in Nigeria have raised 473.52billion Naira.

Basically, from the allocation, it seems when it comes to security, government only spends on the ministries, departments and agencies. This in Nigeria is typically managing and acquiring staffs and weapons for the agencies. These are, the Military, the police, the State Secret Service, the National Intelligence Agency and the National Security Adviser Agency. Please note that no allocation is towards the people in the society.

It is apparent that the government is a subscriber to the tired liberal argument that spending more equals better results. It is however apparent that this is not necessarily true given the continual and even in some cases increment in insecurity which are being experienced through robbery, armed violence and organised acts of

terrorism. This leads to the next issue in perception of insecurity incidents.

Description of the perception of national security will not be complete without touching on insecurity incidents. One of the major insecurity instances in Nigeria is ethno-religious unrest. "Ethnic and the foregoing problems and criminal activities individually and collectively create insecurity and breach of the peace that are likely to or indeed affect legitimate social and economic activities in the country" (Abubakar 2007). Hence, unity and peaceful cooperation of the various ethnicities and religious groups is of importance to avert the frequent crises and violence as well as development deterrents, all of which are perceived insecurity indicators.

Political instability is also a perceived symptom of insecurity. This is because activities of politicians, political parties and elections in the past have sometimes resulted to violence, destruction, deaths and other security breaches. Abubakar (2007) suggests that widespread discontent and loss of confidence in the system are factors that result in political crises.

Today, in Nigeria, the highest mentioned indicator of insecurity is that of organised crime. The most prevailing is that of the terrorist group, 'Boko Haram'. Bombing attacks have been launched at the Police Headquarters in Abuja on 16th June 2011, the 2011 August 26th attack on the United Nations building in Abuja, the Madalla christmas day bombing, all in 2011 and various attacks in other states like Niger, Kano and Borno, even in 2012. These have left Nigerians living in fear e.g. declarations of State of emergencies (e.g. Jos, Suleja in Niger, etc) and restricted freedom of movement through curfews (e.g. in Kano). This is of immense impact as it is not only national but also an international incident and interest. The cornerstone effects are on the expectation the nation has on Nigeria's government, law enforcement agencies and the people. The people's expectations from government are not only press statements and deployment of uniform men to the streets after incidents, but more of what is put in place for prevention, response and rebuilding the society. The law enforcement agency that has been in play the most have been the Nigerian police. What people expect from them include effectiveness of checks and

the effects of corruption which pertain to prevention; the manner and timing of handling incidents, which pertain to response; as well as how effective the security within the Police itself is. The roles the people play are perceived as how vigilant they are in the community and alerting the appropriate agency in events of anomalies.

Ultimately, the context of national security is popularly perceived in terms of amount spent on the activities of our security agencies. National security is also in the minds of many in terms of the presence and prevalence of indicators of insecurities. The way the government go about national security has huge financial and human cost implications. Financial in terms of how much funds is ploughed into security agencies and human in terms of how much human resources are directed towards these agencies as well as those lost during security breach incidences.

The National Security Question - the Reality

This section looks beyond linear interpretation of insecurity from the symptom. The concept of security used to focus on military might and political coercion, but today, it has been recognised to encompass many facets which are not only military but include a lot on economic, social, political, environmental, diplomatic etc security which are all in national security. Thus, this is identification that national security is much more than national defence but also of relations. This concept is yet to be recognised in Nigeria.

In essence, the stance this paper takes is that when it comes to national security, the military aspect is not sole. The aspect this focuses on is going behind the scene of incidents of insecurity. This brings us those who perpetrate such acts in terms of their character or conditions. And then unto the underlying causes that result in such acts of insecurities.

The government of Nigeria in allocating to security agencies only suggests that the only concern is about insecurities by deviants (Iredia 2011), not of securities from other sources and not even seeking to address the deviants themselves which would have given an opportunity to treat insecurity from the depths of its birth. Many

have suggested that insecurity is perpetrated by miscreants, haters of their own people and progress whose sole aim is to unleash terror and inflict harm on the innocent citizens.

Contrary to the above, the group of citizens that perpetrate acts of insecurities have been found to exhibit certain characters. Some of which are strongly linked to poverty especially because when heightened, poverty can reach the extent it breeds and abets rebellion, crime and dissidence. Poverty can be manifested in hunger, homelessness, etc. According to Esiemokhai, "National security begins with food security" (2010), and as the popular saying goes, 'a hungry man is an angry man.' These are typically youths who lack a decent source of livelihood as most are not employed or underemployed.

Furthermore, they are mostly associated with low level and/or poor education. Thus allowing them to be easily brainwashed and influenced into engaging in dastardly acts which they might have been offered meagre amounts for, not have fully thought of and/or not grasped the consequences of their actions to themselves and the rippling effects to others and the society. Such people exposed to these situations have the tendency to become hoodlums, armed robbers, political and ethnic assailants, etc that people need to be protected from.

Aside the character of perpetrators, there are underlying causes which give rise to insecurity incidents. Take joblessness for one, according to Iredia "as our National Bureau of Statistics testifies, there are about 35million unemployed youths in the country who are forced to resort to anything that can serve as means of livelihood" (2011). Source of livelihood is how citizens lead meaningful lives where they can secure food and shelter for themselves, their wards, families (nuclear and extended) and their kins (Esiemokhai 2010). With high rates of unemployment in Nigeria when joblessness has been identified as a cause of deviant behaviour, thus, it should not be a surprise that acts of insecurity will occur.

Corruption has also been identified as a threat to national security. With Nigeria being 143rd out of 183 countries in 2011 according to Transparency

International (2011), while some have not considered it a threat to national security, you can be rest assured it is at play in Nigeria. Corruption is a threat because it deters investment and development. Huge public resources are sapped or deployed away from providing for many due to selfish interest of a few. It leads to undermining the morale of the civil service and affects the quality of goods and services provided. These are basic services like health, road construction, etc which if of low quality can result in fatal consequences and hence, make corruption a security threat.

Others include the huge gap between the rich and the poor which results in tension. There also injustice portrayed where a corrupt officer who embezzled is jailed and released after some months without being mandated to return every kobo that was unauthorized and wrongfully taken.

All the various factors in this section pertain to people, their welfare and well-being. This is human security. Thus, it can be said that the depths of our insecurities is the core of human security.

Myth to Reality: Human security for a secured future

Recent international debates have identified the need to have a broader view of national security. Even the most basic necessities of life like food, water, fuel, medicine and shelter are to be secured. Hence, security is beyond physical/traditional security and human security is necessary to achieve national security (Abubakar, 2007; Esiemokhai 2011; Iredia 2011). Social unrests develop when these basic amenities are lacking.

According to Abubakar (2007), this is already attested to in African countries where government policies have failed to manage properly basic human needs of their citizens. This is the same in Nigeria, where rather than recognizing human security, the language of our national security model is the aggregation of the activities of security agencies (Iredia 2011).

The concept of national security used to focus military might, defence, law enforcement and political coercion alone (Esiemokhai, 2010; Iredia, 2011) but the

concept has now been recognised as encompassing many dimensions, economic, social, environmental, etc. However, National security policy will not be of much use to those who have not satisfied these basic needs and putting huge sums of money will probably be a waste.

National security goes beyond physical security and policing mentality. Addressing problems of insecurities through human security gives the room to tackle the causative aspects of national security i.e. the reality which results in the perceived. This makes human security approach more effective and sustainable. Since if the causal factors are tackled, then the acts will reduce, money ploughed into security agencies could be utilised for other areas. This will move the government from responding to insecurities to actually preventing them.

In essence, government has not made headway because, more spending is not the answer, rather, spending on the appropriate variables is. This is evident in Iredia's statement "even if our entire budget were to be dedicated to dealing with the subject, many people may not raise an eyebrow. For us however, our discomfort is in our government's definition of the term 'security' which seems to harp on the narrow dimension of defence and military might." (Iredia, 2011). Thus there is urgent need for the government to begin to employ other means of addressing insecurities. Human security is the all encompassing measure.

Human security emerged in the international community as a challenge to the traditional security (mostly concern for physical security and emphasises on policing/military might). It is time Nigeria started to challenge its current approach as well. Human security is a people-centred approach which shifts its focus, including responding to people's needs and dealing with not incidents of insecurities, rather, dealing with sources of threats. First of all, human security recognises basic human needs; and pays attention to a wider range of threats to the health and environment, threats to economic deprivation, etc.

The security approach is ultimately looking at national security more broadly, focuses on prevention not cure, looking at security at a more individual level which

individually and collectively results in peace for the nation, and importantly, tackling causative factors and seeking not just to protect but also to empower its citizens, all in line with their human rights.

The categorization of human security approach being broad implies that there is need to redefine security and adopt a measure which addresses all dimensions as they pertain to a nation's economic and environmental securities i.e. address the various insecurities in a cooperative and comprehensive manner. It emphasises removing threats that affect the survival of societies, groups and individuals.

The beauty of the realization of human security implies that the responsibility of security can now be addressed by not only federal government but also at state, local government, NGOs, communities and other organisational group levels. Thus, human security allows for security to be the responsibility of all. This is another facet illustrating human security being a broader all inclusive view of addressing security. Taking human security approach also implies that a method that carries all along is adopted, one which believes in the notion of 'together we rise, divided we fall.' Human security approach combines short-term measures to deal with risks as well as with long-term prevention efforts.

Human security does not only seek to protect people but also seeks to empower people. When people are involved in ensuring their security, they are empowered through education/enlightenment, information and participation in identifying security threats and implementing solutions to insecurities. Empowerment in itself means security as they feel more confident, involved and heard.

Human security is the way forward as it engenders the national security approach. This is important as women are affected by insecurities as well and even sometimes in a different way, they play as much a significant role as men in ensuring lasting human security. In the traditional military approach to national security, threats facing women are always neglected. However, because human security focuses on individuals and believes in carrying all along, women are no exception.

This is of positive contribution as women are sometimes the worst at the receiving end of insecurities. Women have the highest count affected in violence, refugee situations, civilian deaths and cruel and degrading practices, e.g. domestic/spouse violence, assault, harassment, rape, etc. Human security approach as a response to this is to empower women through education and participation. This does not imply that women are prioritised over men, rather, it emphasises the equality which is not present in traditional approach to security.

All in all, human security seeks to identifications of risks, prevention to avoid them through dealing with root causes, preparation to mitigate them and cushioning when disaster strikes i.e. prevention, response, and rebuilding. Nigeria should move to human security as an antidote to insecurity by shifting its security policy from funding security agencies, acquiring more armoury and military armament to that which protects, empowers and promotes human survival, daily life where basic needs of life are readily accessed by its citizens.

Recommendation

Accordingly, government should rethink and redefine security policy and allocation of funds. State and local governments should evolve programmes and participate in ensuring national security. National security should be accepted as responsibility of all and both perceptive and realistic variables should be recognised. A more people-centred approach with focus on individual education and involvement should be adopted. A holistic approach which will recognise and address all form of securities and have concern for causal factors of insecurity incidents should be adopted. For example, the graph below illustrates that while 921.91billion naira was budgeted for security ministries, departments and agencies, allocation to education (400billion), health (283billion) and land & housing (26million) which are basic human needs and part of the root causes of insecurities are not getting as much attention. This highlights the need for human security approach which will consider all factors not just reactive and policing ones.

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Conclusion

Security is not just about reducing violence and destruction. Tackling the underlying structural issues of reducing poverty and offsetting inequalities are far more critical. In this connection and from the prevailing context, three myths around which the current national security response is predicated must be dispelled that:

- insecurity is perpetrated by miscreants whose sole aim is to unleash terror;
- policing and military armament is the immediate and long term response to insecurity;
- there is a dichotomy between personal security (to be assured by individuals) and national security (something to be left to government alone).

In return, the paper calls for a shift from narrow, physical notion of security to a holistic and more sustainable human security paradigm anchored around four central principles:

- Prioritising on human development, including greater emphasis on social protection;
- Enhancing coordinated security apparatus which places emphasis on people (human needs, rights and safety), prevention (not reaction to crisis), protection and empowerment;

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- Shared responsibility for security by all actors, (individuals, government and others);
- Engendering human security for a secure future.

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